

INNOVATIVE LEARNING: CROSSWORD PUZZLE AS A LEARNING TOOL FOR UNDERGRADUATES

Pediatrics

Ekansh Rathoria*	M.D. Paediatrics, Associate professor, Department of Paediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Corresponding Author
Richa Rathoria	M.S. Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Associate professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India.
Utkarsh Bansal	M.D. Paediatrics, Professor and Head, Department of Paediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India.
Anjana Agarwal	M.S. Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Professor and Head, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

Background: Medical education is excogitating every day from traditional learning to innovative learning methods.

Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate the usefulness of Crossword Puzzle as an innovative learning tool and its acceptance by medical undergraduate students.

Methods: This Cross-sectional Observational study was conducted on a purposive sample in Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Barabanki over a period of 3 months from August to October 2020. Four crossword puzzles including 20 questions each on different topics in Paediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynaecology were made after ensuring content validity. Small groups of four students each were made and allowed group discussion to solve crossword puzzle in 10 minutes which was given as Pre-test and Post-test before and after the Lecture respectively. After obtaining informed consent, students were given a questionnaire identifying cognitive, affective and applied aspects of learning domains and asked to respond on a 5-point Likert scale.

Results: Total 26 groups of 4 students each participated (n=104). Total Mean (standard deviation) of four Pre-test and Post-test scores were 8.47(1.44) and 16.18(1.95) respectively (p-value < 0.00001). The merits of crossword puzzle listed by students: identifying key concepts (91.35%), enhanced knowledge (91.35%), promoted cognitive/mental skills and attitude (92.31%), satisfactory (87.5%), recommended to incorporate in teaching curriculum (87.5%), and promoted active learning by collaborative and competitive aspects (91.35%).

Conclusions: Student's perceptions indicate the usefulness of crossword puzzles to endorse positive learning in an interactive environment and advocates their use as an adjunct to lecture thereby allowing easy recall of the content.

KEYWORDS

Crossword puzzle, Innovative learning tool, Medical Education

INTRODUCTION

Medical undergraduate students have to go through a vast syllabus and learn various concepts in a short time period. Passive lectures deliver basic theoretical knowledge and is one-way communication thus providing the lowest knowledge retention rate and the lowest level of cognitive function.¹ Thus, it's the need of the hour to discover and indoctrinate new creative ideas and innovations in our education system to complement the traditional lectures and augment learning by utilizing active strategies like small group discussion, debates, role-play, multiple choice questions, quiz, and puzzle solving.^{2,3}

Students' interest and retention of knowledge in the subject may be increased by educational games.⁴ The benefits of active learning strategies like interactive puzzles and games are manifold as they help in involvement of different skills like attitude, concept building, cognition, communication, critical thinking, learning, and motivation among students.⁵

Using Crossword puzzle game during didactic lectures not only breaks the monotony but also helps in active involvement of students thus improving critical thinking and boosting their cognitive skills.^{6,7} Small group discussion to solve crossword puzzles by making teams promotes team work and also complements the traditional method of teaching.⁸ Small group discussion helps students to discuss key concepts and ideas thus improving their critical thinking and problem-solving skills.⁹

The aim of our study was to evaluate the usefulness of Crossword Puzzle as an innovative learning tool and its acceptance by medical undergraduate students.

METHODS

This Cross-sectional Observational study was conducted in Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki over a period of 3 months from August to October 2020 after obtaining approval from

institute's ethical committee. A sample size of 104 medical students of IIIrd Professional Part II were included in study by purposive sample method after obtaining informed consent from them.

We conducted four crossword puzzles exercises in Paediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynaecology on the topics Protein energy malnutrition, Immunization, Neonatal resuscitation and Normal delivery. It took around 4-5 hours to prepare a moderate difficulty level crossword puzzle with relevant content and around 25 minutes to complete this exercise with answer discussion in class.

Crossword puzzle were created using 20 horizontal and 20 vertical spaces and total 20 questions with clues were designed in this framework which were divided into 10 horizontal and 10 vertical space questions and a final draft was created after going through multiple drafts [Annexure 1]. The final draft was reviewed and approved by respective departmental faculty after authentication that the format, content and concept of the crossword puzzle was adequate for that topic under study. After faculty approval, a pilot testing was done on peers and assuring that puzzle could be used as a learning tool and for validation of the answers. To avoid bias, a faculty member other than who prepared the crossword puzzle took the formal lecture.

Before the formal lecture of the topic, students were randomized to make groups of 4 students each and the crossword puzzle was given to these small groups as a Pre-test. There were 20 clues, which ranged from easy to difficult, to be solved in 10 min. Students in a group were allowed to discuss among themselves regarding the questions. Next, the formal teaching of the topic was done by a faculty in the form of a lecture class or demonstration. Following that, the same crossword puzzle was given to be solved in 10 minutes as a post-test allowing group discussion to finish this exercise in a synergetic manner. After student groups completed the Post-test, the answers were discussed to clarify any doubts. Scoring for each group was done with 1 mark for each correct answer with maximum 20 marks.

Outcome measures - After completion of all the four exercises, they were given a questionnaire regarding the experience with the exercise. The students were asked to respond anonymously on a 5-point Likert scale where 1,2,3,4,5 was strongly disagreed, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree respectively. Following questions were framed to assess the cognitive, affective and applied aspects of learning domains.

Cognitive learning domain: -

1. The Crossword puzzles were useful in identifying key concepts in studied topics.
2. The Crossword puzzles enhanced my knowledge in studied topics.
3. The Crossword puzzles promotes cognitive/mental skill as well as attitude.
4. Crossword puzzle exercise was Satisfactory.
5. Crossword Puzzles like this should be given after each topic class and should be included in our teaching curriculum.

Affective learning Domain: -

1. The material on the crossword puzzles was pertinent to the topic studied.
2. Duration of time provided for solving the puzzles was sufficient.
3. Solving crossword puzzle was as an enjoyable experience.
4. Solving crossword puzzle was a waste of time.
5. Crossword Puzzles were easy.
6. Crossword Puzzles were difficult.

Applied Aspect: -

1. Group discussion while solving crossword puzzle helped in building concepts on studied topics.
2. The crossword puzzles promote active learning by collaborative and competitive aspects.
3. Crossword puzzle is an overall useful learning tool and promotes self-learning.

Data Analysis

Mean, standard deviation, Paired Student's "t" test for comparing pre-test and post-test scores and p-value were calculated using SPSS software version 17, (P < 0.05 being statistically significant). Descriptive statistics were used for individual question analysis from Likert's scale data.

RESULTS

Total 26 groups of 4 students each participated in this exercise (n=104) on four topics. Total Mean (standard deviation) of four Pre-test and Post-test scores were 8.47 (1.44) and 16.18 (1.95) respectively (t-value 40.66, p-value<0.00001) [Table 1].

TABLE 1: - PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST SCORE COMPARISON REPRESENTING ENHANCEMENT IN LEARNING (N=104)

Topics	Pre-test Mean (SD)	Post-test Mean (SD)	t-value	p-value*
Protein Energy Malnutrition	7.61 (1.11)	15.07 (1.79)	15.83	< .00001
Neonatal resuscitation	8.42 (1.27)	16.53 (1.84)	21.04	< .00001
Immunization	9.38 (1.07)	17.03 (1.58)	22.11	< .00001
Normal delivery	8.46 (1.66)	16.07 (2.01)	25.03	< .00001
Total	8.47 (1.44)	16.18 (1.95)	40.66	< .00001

* Statistically significant (p-value<0.05)

Total 104 medical undergraduate students responded on Crossword puzzle feedback form. The 14 question-based feedback form covered numerous aspects of the new learning tool as adjunct to traditional lecture. Responses to the enhanced cognitive, affective and applied aspects of learning domains are shown in Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 respectively.

TABLE 2: - STUDENTS RESPONSES REPRESENTING COGNITIVE LEARNING DOMAIN (N=104)*

Questions	SD No. (%)	D No. (%)	N No. (%)	A No. (%)	SA No. (%)
Useful in identifying key concepts	3 (2.89)	0 (0)	6 (5.77)	35 (33.65)	60 (57.69)
Enhanced knowledge	2 (1.92)	1 (0.96)	6 (5.77)	30 (28.85)	65 (62.5)
Promotes cognitive/mental skill as well as attitude.	1 (0.96)	1 (0.96)	6 (5.77)	21 (20.19)	75 (72.12)
Satisfactory	1 (0.96)	2 (1.92)	10 (9.62)	32 (30.77)	59 (56.73)
Recommended Crossword Puzzles exercise to be included in the teaching curriculum	2 (1.92)	2 (1.92)	9 (8.65)	41 (39.43)	50 (48.08)

*SD = Strongly disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly agree

TABLE 3: - STUDENTS RESPONSES REPRESENTING AFFECTIVE LEARNING DOMAIN (N=104)*

Questions	SD No. (%)	D No. (%)	N No. (%)	A No. (%)	SA No. (%)
The material was pertinent to the topic studied.	1 (0.96)	1 (0.96)	9 (8.65)	30 (28.85)	63 (60.58)
Duration of time provided was sufficient.	1 (0.96)	2 (1.92)	12 (11.54)	38 (36.54)	51 (49.04)
Easy	5 (4.81)	15 (14.42)	51 (49.04)	21 (20.19)	12 (11.54)
Difficult.	1 (0.96)	8 (7.7)	57 (54.8)	26 (25)	12 (11.54)
Solving crossword puzzle was a waste of time	70 (67.31)	12 (11.54)	6 (5.77)	9 (8.65)	7 (6.73)
Enjoyable experience.	1 (0.96)	1 (0.96)	8 (7.7)	22 (21.15)	72 (69.23)

*SD = Strongly disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly agree

TABLE 4: - STUDENTS RESPONSES REPRESENTING APPLIED ASPECTS OF LEARNING DOMAIN (N=104)*

Questions	SD No. (%)	D No. (%)	N No. (%)	A No. (%)	SA No. (%)
Promote active learning by collaborative and competitive aspects	2 (1.92)	1 (0.96)	6 (5.77)	28 (26.93)	67 (64.42)
Group discussion helped in building concepts on studied topics.	2 (1.92)	4 (3.85)	7 (6.73)	24 (23.08)	67 (64.42)
Overall useful learning tool and promotes self-learning.	1 (0.96)	1 (0.96)	9 (8.65)	32 (30.77)	61 (58.66)

*SD = Strongly disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly agree

DISCUSSION

In present study, there was a significant improvement in post-test scores as compared to pre-test scores indicating improvement in learning which was akin to study done by Malini M et al who found

highly significant difference in pre-test and post-test scores.¹⁰

In present study, we reported positive cognitive domain responses i.e., crossword puzzle exercise was helpful in identifying key concepts, enhanced their knowledge, promoted cognitive/mental skills and attitude, satisfactory and recommended that it should be included in our teaching curriculum after each topic class. Our findings were comparable to study done by Saran R et al where most of students favoured that crossword puzzle aided better learning and understanding of the topic and they strongly recommended adding it in their curriculum.¹¹ The study by N Gaikwad et al also recommended crossword puzzle to be incorporated in the curriculum.⁵

With respect to affecting affective learning domain in our study, majority of students acquiesced that the material on the crossword puzzles was pertinent to the topic studied, duration of time provided for solving the puzzles was sufficient and considered it as an enjoyable experience. Similar study by S Shah et al found 98.8% students agreed that material on the puzzle was pertinent and 94.9% said the length of time provided for solving puzzles was sufficient.⁷ N Gaikwad et al reported that 82.86% students strongly agreed it as an enjoyable experience.⁵

In present study, 31.73% students accepted that crossword puzzles were easy while 36.54% accepted as difficult. 78.85% students dissented that solving crossword puzzle was a waste of time. These findings were analogous to study done by U Gupta et al, where 21.37% and 32.48% students accepted this crossword puzzle exercise as easy and difficult respectively while 69.23% students disagreed to this as waste of time.¹²

In present study, regarding applied aspects of crossword puzzle, students favoured that the crossword puzzle exercise promoted active learning by collaborative and competitive aspects, group discussion helped in building concepts on studied topic and an overall useful learning tool and promotes self-learning. This was similar to study done by S Manzar and SM Al-Khusaiby which showed that crossword puzzle exercise stimulated interactive learning shown by their positive attitude and response in a small group teaching.¹³ The study done by S Patrick et al. observed that crossword puzzle as an adjunct tool improved students' attitude of learning and performance.¹⁴

CONCLUSIONS

The biggest challenge for teachers is to provide education which inspires students. The teaching learning methodology should be engaging the student which makes it a two-way learning. The perceptions from our study indicate the usefulness of crossword puzzles to endorse positive learning in an interactive environment and advocates their use as an adjunct to lecture thereby allowing them to recall the lecture material. These innovative learning tools like crossword puzzle exercises could be included in teaching curriculum.

There were some limitations in present study:

1. This method only focused on merits of crossword puzzle and did not compared it with other educational games like debates, role-play, multiple choice questions quiz.
2. Long term retention benefits of the topic were not analysed.
3. As we employed small group discussion methodology, the acceptance at individual level cannot be assessed.
4. As it was done at one centre only, generalization of results may not be possible.

Further evaluation of crossword puzzles in a multicentre approach is needed to assess its feasibility in medical education.

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DECLARATIONS

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ANNEXURE 1

ANNEXURE 1 : NEONATAL RESUSCITATION PROGRAM CROSSWORD PUZZLE

HORIZONTAL

1. Before birth, oxygen is supplied to the foetus by the _____.
2. An exceptionally strong man should be prepared with the patient and over the mother's _____.
3. 500 grams include 1000 words. Parents to have a rich, clear vocabulary. **HEAD** _____ **PHYSIOLOGY**.
4. A mother is expected to do not improve with the fetal steps or possible pressure ventilation. Her heart rate remains 60 beats per minute. An endotracheal tube is placed properly the chest is moving, bilateral breath sounds are present.

- and ventilation has continued for another 20 seconds. Her heart rate is still 60 beats per minute. _____ should be started.
5. Ventilation that covers the chest has been performed through an endotracheal tube for 30 seconds and associated with chest compressions and 100% oxygen for an additional 30 seconds. If the baby's heart rate remains below 60 beats per minute, you should give _____ while continuing chest compressions and ventilation.
6. The preferred route for nebulized _____.
7. Babies with a known or suspected diaphragmatic hernia should not receive prolonged intubation with _____ as first step.
8. In an emergency a _____ may be selected by decreased breath sounds and increased transillumination in the affected side.
9. When using suction to clear secretions, first suction the mouth's _____.
10. A patient who has had significant birth depression and required a complete resuscitation. He has continued respiratory failure with CO₂ retention and a metabolic acidosis. _____ should not be used immediately after resuscitation.

VERTICAL

11. Before birth, the air sacs in the fetal lungs are expanded and filled with _____.
12. The single most important and most effective step in neonatal resuscitation is _____ of the lungs.
13. Positive pressure ventilation is indicated if the baby is apnoeic or _____ or the heart rate is less than 100 beats per minute after the initial steps.
14. The preferred nebulized beta-2 agonist for use in a _____ newborn is **Sal**.
15. Both right- and left-handed people should hold the laryngoscope in their _____ hand.
16. In the absence of fluid or airway disease blood flow, routine administration of a _____ is not recommended.
17. Pre-ductal SpO₂ is measured in _____ ligamentum.
18. The correct depth of chest compressions is approximately _____ of the anteroposterior diameter of the chest.
19. During chest compressions, pressure should be applied to the _____ third of the sternum.
20. Suction is _____ if a newborn has respiratory distress and generalized edema (hydrothorax).

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